

SCAN ME!

INTRODUCTION

- Despite its potential, **radiomics** [1] faces significant stability challenges, primarily due to the variability in image acquisition and segmentation, which impacts the reproducibility of extracted features [2].
- Recently, **Deep Learning** (DL) techniques have emerged as the gold standard for **medical image segmentation**, offering superior accuracy and precision compared to traditional methods.
- The integration of DL models in the radiomics workflow has shown potential to improve the **reproducibility of the radiomic features**, by ensuring a more accurate and reproducible automatic delineation of the regions of interest (ROIs).
- However, a key challenge is the lack of transparency in the model's confidence regarding its predictions, raising concerns about the reliability of segmentations. **Uncertainty estimation in DL-based segmentation** could be a valid solution for this issue.

AIM

- This study aims to investigate whether quantifying segmentation uncertainty can provide an automated solution to address intra- and inter-observer **variability in segmentation**, as well as **variability in image acquisition**, both of which affect the reliability of radiomics.
- The central question to answer is:

Does extracting features only from confidently segmented regions improve radiomics robustness compared to extracting features from all segmented regions without considering uncertainty?

METHODS

NETWORK ARCHITECTURES

- Deterministic U-Net**: the 2D U-Net, as implemented by [3], is used as reference model.
- U-Net for Segmentation Uncertainty Estimation**:
 - Monte Carlo Dropout (MCD)** [4]: dropout layers are inserted and kept active in both training and testing phases, generating T different predictions for each test input image.
 - Test-Time Augmentation (TTA)** [5]: the deterministic U-Net is trained and used at test time to make predictions over T different augmented versions of the input image.

Figure 1. U-Net extended to apply MCD for uncertainty estimation.

Data Augmentation	Random Shifts, Zoom, Rotations, Shears
Loss Function	Dice Loss
Metric	Dice Score Coefficient (DSC)
N° Epochs	100
Batch Size	16
Optimizer	Adam (lr 10 ⁻⁴)
Dropout rate (for MCD)	0.25
T (N° of MCD/TTA Predictions)	50

Table 1. Training parameters.

ROIs DEFINITION AND RADIOMIC FEATURES EXTRACTION

- The **Ground Truth (GT) mask** is the manually segmented mask included in the dataset.
- The **Deterministic Prediction (DP) mask** is obtained from the deterministic U-Net model.
- To delineate masks reflecting different Levels of Confidence in segmentation (**CL masks**), thresholds th for agreement among the 50 MCD/TTA predictions are established, ranging from 0.1 to 1 with a 0.1 step size.
- 105 radiomic features** are extracted using Pyradiomics package in Python from GT, DP and CL masks, for all test acquisitions.

REPRODUCIBILITY ANALYSIS

- Reproducibility to segmentation variability is assessed by Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC) type 3 between manually and automatically delineated kidney regions (ICC_S).
- Reproducibility to acquisition variability is estimated by ICC type 2 among the 5 scan repetitions per subject on the kidney mask (ICC_A).
- The analysis is done with and without including segmentation uncertainty information.
- For each analysis, features are classified in 4 classes based on ICC_S and ICC_A values.

Figure 2. (A) Workflow for ROIs definition. Reproducibility analysis without (B) and with (C) segmentation uncertainty information.

	ICC _S ≥ 0.8	ICC _S < 0.8
ICC _A ≥ 0.8	Class 1	Class 2
ICC _A < 0.8	Class 3	Class 4

Table 2. Criteria for features classification.

DATASET

- T2-weighted coronal kidney MRI scans of 60 subjects (30 with Chronic Kidney Disease – CKD, and 30 Healthy Controls - HC) from a public repository [3], along with manually segmented kidney masks.
- 10 subjects (5 CKD, 5 HC) underwent scanning five times within a single session. These data (650 2D slices) are used as test data and for the radiomic analysis.
- The data (649 2D slices) from the other 50 subjects (25 CKD, 25 HC), scanned once, are used for the training of the models (80% training, 20% validation), together with the GT masks.

Figure 3. Example of an MRI slice with the manual contour of the kidneys (in green): (A) CKD subject and (B) HC subject.

RESULTS

SEGMENTATION ACCURACY

- In terms of segmentation accuracy, the performance of MCD and TTA methods is comparable.
- For MCD, the DSC is 0.93 on HC and 0.91 on CKD subjects, whereas TTA achieves 0.93 on HC and 0.90 on CKD subjects.

REPRODUCIBILITY ANALYSIS RESULTS

- Without accounting for segmentation uncertainty information, most of the features are classified into class 4.
- For all methods, and for both CKDs and HCs, there is a consistent trend: as th increases, the n° of features in class 4 decreases, while the n° of features in class 3 increases, up to a certain th defined optimal threshold th_{opt} .
- For HCs, the n° of features in class 1 increases too.

Figure 4. N° of features in each class, without uncertainty information and at different th , for the two methods and for CKD and HC subjects separately. The circled th corresponds to the optimal threshold for uncertainty th_{opt} .

- As th increases, more internal regions of the kidney are selected as confidently segmented ROIs.
- TTA predictions show greater variability, as increasing th leads to smaller ROIs being identified as confidently segmented.

Figure 5. GT contour and contours with different th (0.1, th_{opt} , 1), for MCD (A) and TTA (B) approaches.

CONCLUSIONS

- Acquisition variability consistently influences outcomes, while segmentation variability is particularly pronounced in CKDs due to lower accuracy.
- Incorporating an uncertainty-informed ROI segmentation step into the radiomics pipeline significantly enhances reproducibility against acquisition variability for both CKD and HC subjects, consistently across both MCD and TTA methods.
- Reproducibility related to segmentation variability improves only in HCs and remains unaffected in CKDs, due to the complex anatomy of diseased kidneys.

REFERENCES

- P. Lambin *et al.*, "Radiomics: Extracting more information from medical images using advanced feature analysis", *Eur J Cancer*, vol. 48, no. 4, pp. 441–446, Mar. 2012, doi: 10.1016/J.EJCA.2011.11.036.
- E. Scalco *et al.*, "The stability of oncologic MRI radiomic features and the potential role of deep learning: A review", *Physics in Medicine and Biology*, vol. 67, no. 9, IOP Publishing Ltd, May 07, 2022, doi: 10.1088/1361-6560/ac6b09.
- A. J. Daniel *et al.*, "Automated renal segmentation in healthy and chronic kidney disease subjects using a convolutional neural network", *Magn Reson Med*, vol. 86, no. 2, pp. 1125–1136, Aug. 2021, doi: 10.1002/mrm.28768.
- Gal, Yarin, and Zoubin Ghahramani. "Dropout as a bayesian approximation: Representing model uncertainty in deep learning", 2016.
- G. Wang *et al.*, "Aleatoric uncertainty estimation with test-time augmentation for medical image segmentation with convolutional neural networks", *Neurocomputing* 338, 34–45 (2019).

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